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TALENT MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AND THEIR IMPACT ON EMPLOYEE JOB PERFORMANCE IN THE NIGER MILLS COMPANY LIMITED

Jordan A. Smith

Department of Human Resource Management, School of Business, University of California, Berkeley, CA 94720, USA

Email: jordan.smith@berkeley.edu

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Abstract: The effective engagement of employees, turnover intentions, and job knowledge are affected by talent war in a knowledge environment. This study examined talent retention, job satisfaction, and training and development as proxies for effective job performance. Resource Base View with emphasis on the employee as a strategic resource that enhances competitive advantage was adopted to guide the study. A cross-sectional survey research design was adopted with a sample size of 142 staff. The questionnaire tagged TMPEJP facilitated data collection and was analyzed using Multicollinearity with Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). The instrument was developed, validated, and tested for reliability using Cronbach Alpha. Multiple Regression Analysis was used to test the hypotheses using SPSS. Findings revealed that talent retention significantly influences employee job performance (Beta = 0.545, $P < 0.05$). Job satisfaction significantly influences employee job performance (Beta = 0.756, $P < 0.05$). Training and development significantly influence employee job performance (Beta = 0.692, $P < 0.05$). It concluded that increased productivity in a competitive environment requires effective use of resources to sustain competitive advantage. The study recommended that the management of the organization should continuously show commitment to talent retention with a policy review based on current realities to help the organization boost productivity with increasing revenue and minimize turnover. Priority for job satisfaction should be uncompromised to increase morale and productivity through happiness, and a positive workplace culture to enhance effective job performance. Training and development should be a continuous practice for competitive advantage with the allocation of resources to improve the company culture and performance level of employees to meet their tasks.

Keywords: Talent retention, Job satisfaction, and Training and development.

Introduction

The emergence of talent management practice in the 19th century has made a significant number of organizations come to the realization of achieving the organizational target through employee talents (Tyskbo, 2019, p.1614). Globally, talent management has been a challenge for HR professionals with the emergence of volatility and

Original Article

dynamics in the business environment (Almohtaseb et al. 2020, p.13; Meyers & van Woerkom, 2014, p.195). The effectiveness of talent management is driven by qualitative and quantitative skills with the aim of placing workers in the right positions for optimal performance. Many studies have advocated talent management as a measure for improving organizational performance and competitive advantage (Meyers et al., 2013, p.307; Gruman & Saks, 2011, p.125). Many organizations have considered it as a strategy that supports competence for employee development, enhancement of competence, etc. However, the adoption of global talent management best practices and the need for a local labour market have affirmed the requirements talent management approach (Almohtaseb et al. 2020, p.15).

Today, the rapid transition in HR management practice has transitioned from locating and retaining talent to creating talent. Organizational leaders have become creative in managing the complexity of talent (Kashive & Khanna, 2017, p.175). Therefore, the present candidate-driven market in the manufacturing sector has imposed issues on recruiters coupled with the lack of qualified applicants that organizations seek to hire in the midst of fierce competition. The slow adaptation of HR in various industries in the past has encountered a paradigm shift due to a change in the hiring climate. The emergence of technology and the continuous prevalence of social media has created the need for cutting-edge technology for hiring the best workers and retaining the top talent.

In a contemporary work environment, private and public organizations have prioritized talent management as an attractive tool to attract, retain, and develop employees. This is achieved through the procedures of identifying and developing employees into leadership capabilities. In the manufacturing sector in Nigeria, talent acquisition, hiring, and retention have become more difficult due to changes imposed by the market. Based on this, this study seeks to examine

Statement of the problem

Talent wars among organizations have made talent management efforts a struggle caused by higher demand and a shortage of skilled labour. With the scarcity of human resources and skills shortage, competition has become fiercer than before. This has imposed a dilemma as talent is seen as an attractive source of competitive advantage and organizations with talent shortages are unable to attract and retain talented workers the organization.

Firms in the manufacturing sector in Nigeria are affected by the dynamics in the contemporary business environment which have influenced the continuous practice of talent management due to competition, economic political, and technological factors. Also, the inability to give talent the first priority offers difficulty in attracting and retaining talent in the organization.

Implementing talent management practice is bedeviled with the inability to create an opportunity for a talent pool to identify talent through talent retention, lack of job satisfaction, and training and development. These have been caused by unforeseen situations which make it difficult to ascertain the various positions needed in the future. Hence, the lack of talented workers has resulted in poor performance of the organization. Based on this backdrop, this study examines talent management practice and employee job performance in NIGER Mills Company Limited Calabar, Cross River State.

Objectives of the study

The specific objectives of the study are:

1. To examine how talent retention is used to reduce turnover to enhance employee job performance in Niger Mills Company Limited Calabar
2. To examine how job satisfaction is used to promote employee engagement to enhance employee job performance in Niger Mills Company Limited Calabar
3. To examine how training and development promote job knowledge to enhance employee job performance in Niger Mills Company Limited Calabar

Theoretical framework

This study adopted a Resource Base View as a theoretical framework to guide the study. The theory stresses the need for competitive advantage to be acquired through efforts to develop both organizational and human resources

Original Article

in a manner that could add sustainable and unique value to the organization (Barney, 1991, p.101). With Resource Base View, a firm has a strong focus on internal unique resources over external resources which comprises intellectual and physical resources to enhance talent, performance, and competitive advantage (Newbert, 2007, p.747).

Resource Base View is attributed to internal resources that are rare, non-substitutable, inimitable, and valuable. In the context of the Resource Base View, Barney (1991, p.103) emphasizes that value is the resources exploited to enhance organizational opportunities that are not acquired by other competitors in the same market. Also, an imitable resource implies that difficult for other competitor to reproduce or copy for their benefit. The nonsubstitutability of resources is the absence of similar resources to serve a similar purpose in the market. Hence, an organization with non-substitutable, imitable, and valuable resources practically affirmed the Resource Base View theoretical and practical status. This study enables the organization to gain the expected competitive advantage in the market.

The justifications of this theory to the study are that it educates organizational leaders to understand that talented employee is a strategic resource that increasingly enhances the performance of an organization or competitive advantage. This indicates that Resource Base View underpins high performance through the use of talented employee based on their skills, knowledge, attitude, and motivation. Organizational leaders are able to use the available resources to gain leverage over competitors in the market through the recruitment of talented workers to achieve the set goals of the organization.

Conceptual framework

Figure 1: Talent Management Practice in Niger Mills Company Limited

Concept of talent management

The concept of talent has no clear-cut definition because it is defined differently in the environment. Rather it is defined based on specific capabilities, goals, and vision that that organization is required to achieve (Bolander et al., 2017). On the other hand, talent management as a concept is multifaceted and competition for talent has made HR practitioners build talent management on strategic human resource management. Talent management has attracted the interest of researchers with a primary focus on high-quality of human capital. For instance, having special skills and abilities and applying them for sustainable benefits of the organization (Tarique & Schuler, 2017, p.80). Tyskbo (2019, p.1614) see talent management as strategic activities, practices, methods, or processes that require the HR manager to identify, key positions in the organization and fill them with high-performing or competent individual to enhance the performance of the organization with commitment. Similarly, Collings et al. (2019, p.542) support that talent management involves attracting, identifying, retaining and using individuals with

Original Article

human capital with significant value to the growth of the organization. Al Ariss et al. (2014, p.175) conceptualize the relevance of talent management as a means for an organization to effectively hold on to talents and have the ability to retain the talent for a longer period. It involves the improvement in business value through the scientific use of strategic human resource planning. Talent management helps to create, attract, and retain talent within the organization (Tarique & Schuler, 2017, p.82). This has made many organizations to be attractive employers with a motive of attracting, motivating, and retaining talented employees (Kashive & Khanna, 2017, p.175). Talent management is an attractive practice to organizations with the ability to secure the human capital, and competitive advantage of the organization. The concept of talent management is envisaged to comprise career development which allows workers to develop themselves to secure a career future (Lee et al., 2020, p.103). Talent management as a practice requires investment in the best workers through developing them, building and leveraging their potential and strength to improve their weakness. In the words of Gupta and Haque (2015, p.20) talent management entails implementing integrated strategies that have been designed to optimize productivity in the workplace with the aim of improving, the talent management processes to attract, develop, retain, and utilize people with the needed skills to achieve the organizational goals

Talent retention and job performance

Conceptually, employee retention is a continuous, formal, systematic, consistent, and holistic process and methodology used by an organizational leader to ensure that trusted talent is retained in the organization (El Sayed et al., 2021, p.641). This implies an internal and external search for talent while developing criteria for the effective selection of the right competence to enhance the productivity of the organization. The mission and value of an organization are dependent on the development of leaders with experience to support the realization of organizational goals (Kuvaas, et al, 2016, p.668). An HR resource manager is faced with issues of retaining a talented workforce or those seeking to leave the organization. Therefore, a study by Covella (2017, p. 5) suggests the use of tested and tried strategies in retaining the best staff of an organization. This affirmed that the critical task of talent management is retaining employees to contribute to the success of the organization. (El Sayed et al. (2021, p.642) support that effective contribution to organization growth through retention is by motivating and developing the loyalty of employees, investing in employee careers, and rewarding financial and non-financially. An outward practice of managing, training, and developing employee talent are measure that indicates that organizational leaders have an interest in them. Kuvaas, et al. (2016, p.669) suggests two types of incentives for retaining talented employees. For instance, the use of internal incentives relates to the non-financial reward that is adopted to satisfy the psychological needs of employees. On the other hand, the extrinsic reward is the monetary reward used in fulfilling the psychological needs and retaining the talent of the employee. Narayanan (2019, p.229) supports that the strategic means of retaining workers is to adopt the culture of spreading talent to achieve excellence and competitive advantage in the organization; give support to talent management across all units of the organization; and allow the talented employee to participate in the management of crisis and problem that could affect the attainment of organizational goals

The possession of potential job-specific qualifications by graduates and the existence of jobseeking agencies allow the recruitment of candidates into the organization. The effort made by organizations to retain employees is aimed at enhancing productivity and achieving the set goals of an organization (Naim & Lenka 2018, p.53). For instance, the level of turnover in every sector of business is linked to the reassignment of workers leading to the failed attainment of organizational goals (El Sayed et al., 2021, p.643). This indicates the need to give adequate attention to employee retention as a measure to reduce turnover and costs associated with recruitment and training. Consequently, an employee who quits job is attributed to a loss of customer loyalty and experience and this constitutes costs, disruption of activities, and loss of resources. Hence, Covella (2017, p.7) considers this as disastrous to organizational growth

Effective identification and stimulation of talent are important factors for enhancing competitive advantage in a present business environment. The possession of capabilities and skills are excellent forces for the present and

Original Article

future success of the organization (Harathova 2009, p.54). This is because the influence of commercialization supports the quest for improved performance for organizational success. The necessity of retention strategies is aimed at ensuring the talent pool contributes to the future needs of the organization. For instance, a study by Ibidunni et al (2016, p.6) indicates that 68 percent of organizational leaders believe that retaining talent for competitive advantage is better than acquiring talent to improve productivity. Hence, effective retention of talent is an extraordinary effort in employer-employee aimed at retaining talent.

The need to retain top talents in organizations has been an issue facing HR. This is because the need to improve the economy and expand the job market has made workers swayed by a corporate culture which complicates recruitment and retention. Therefore, the HR professional is able to improve recruitment and retention through flexible work arrangements to retain top talent, promote openness and trust among employees, establish attractive reward packages then competitors, and offer career advancement

Job satisfaction and job performance

With the complex global economy that is characterized as hypercompetitive, job satisfaction has constituted a serious challenge that many organizations are faced with as HR managers are continuously involved in developing policies to manage the employees. Job satisfaction connotes a favourable and positive attitude to the job (Rani & Kumar, 2014, p.25). It implies the contentment of employee in workplace which is a growing issues in organizations across the globe (Dixit & Arrawatia, 2018, p.427). The satisfaction of employee offered by the organization make them to share the worthiness and network to achieve the overall goals and objectives of organization (Tanwar & Prasad, 2016, p.15).

The extent of employee engagement is considered as a determinant of job satisfaction of employees which enhances business success (Lockwood et al., 2006, p.1). Rani and Kumar (2014, p.27) noted that the collective choice of individual and organization is based on complimentary personalities for both to fit into each other and job satisfaction is represented by the employee personality fit to the organization.

A study by Gomathy, et al. (2022, p.3) identified four factors that influence job satisfaction for talented workers to be retained. For instance, paying higher incentive to employee make them happy with their jobs when compared with those that don't have high incentives. In addition, a healthy work environment accords significant value to employees. Two, work-life balance is influenced by ethical workplace which allows employees to have for their family and friends. The policy of good work-life balance constitutes job satisfaction to the talented employee and also improves the work life of an employee. Three, job security is a guarantee that gives confidence and satisfaction to employees when employed in an organization irrespective of the turbulent market caused by external factors. Lastly, career growth is one priority of employees when they are groomed by the organization. This proffers job satisfaction which helps to boost their career

A survey by Siripipatthanakul et al. (2022, p.2) revealed the importance of HR personnel, retention agents' or managers to acquire an understanding of employee satisfaction and loyalty. This is because increasing responsiveness, productivity, customer service, and quality are dependent on the extent to which the employee is delighted or satisfied (Sageer et al., 2012, p.34). This indicated that the satisfaction of employee is influenced by goal attainment, motivation, and how their needs are met with positive workplace morale.

Talent management influences job satisfaction through effective performance which enhances the profitability of an organization (Santhanalaxmi & Chandramohan 2019, p.422). This is because in both product and service markets, a business is faced with a competitor and the need for talent becomes uncompromising. Abolade (2021, p.7) conceptualizes the effective and efficient performance of an organization as an off-shot of job satisfaction of employees which makes employees committed to their engagement in the organization. For instance, the achievement of positive performance is driven by the management of resources and alignment with the objective of the organization.

Original Article

Training and development and job performance

A talented employee is driven by training and development at any stage of the organization. For instance, 70 percent of a training programme that is available in an organization helps to increase their rate of retention, and career development allows a professional to acquire the needed skills and knowledge and grow in their career choice (Eisen, 2005, p.15). Motivating talented employees is not limited to higher incentives but through open communication and career development

The continuous learning and growth of employee are capacity that makes them unwilling to leave the organization with the acquired talent. On the other hand, the absence of learning for growth is a factor that makes employees seek to leave by looking for job opportunities outside (Rodriguez, 2008). In the contemporary workplace, coaching is used to develop workers and this serves as motivation to talented workers in an effective way (Farndale et al., 2014, p.207). The use of coaching makes high-performing workers unwilling to leave as they are continuously engaged and motivated to achieve the set goals

A study by Mpofu and Hlatywayo (2015, p.135) revealed that employee willingness to be trained and developed is a core priority of recruiting the workforce into the organization. This implies that with the continuous changes in the external environment, there is a need for effective development of the workforce to address organizational issues to enhance competitive advantage and meet the objective of the organization. The effectiveness of the training and development is dependent on the synergy between the employer and the employee to ensure the objective of training and development is for problem-solving

However, HRM in the 21st century is faced with increasing pressure on talent. This is because the objective of securing a high-quality talented workforce with potential growth in the labour market has made the process of retaining and developing employee to be competitive. Tatoglu et al. (2016, p.279) support training plays an important function in investing in the future of employees while development is a strategic source that allows people to undertake their assigned performance for present and future tasks. Development is a way of changing the workforce based on training that is planned or unplanned to achieve the desired competitive advantage. Hence, training and development help to prepare for the emerging change that may emanate.

The continuous reason for training and development as a priority is for innovation and inventions to be used to achieve competitive advantage (Meyers & Van Woerkom, 2014, p.196). This indicates that new solutions to problems affect the way organizations seek to treat workers based on their interest

Measures of employee job performance

Employee performance is driven by resourcefulness and actions that employees take to meet the set goals and objectives of an organization (Gomathy, et al., 2022, p.3). Increased productivity in the organization is influenced by performance assessment which offers feedback with the right behaviour to ensure that the systematic process of collecting and analyzing information helps in determining the efficiency and effectiveness of employee attainment of objectives (Pawirosumarto et al., 2017, p.13). According to Siripipatthanakul et al. (2022, p.6), performance relates to the extent of effectiveness on reliability, availability, output, cost efficiency, time, etc. Employee job performance allows the use of operational capacity to enhance the survival of the organization and meet the needs of shareholders. This is done by evaluating organizational success based on business performance and talent management (Limsangpetch et al., 2022, p.5).

Altindağ et al. (2018, p.11) note that employee performance has shifted concern on how higher HR resource influences business performance. This is because the implementation of talent management has helped identify, deploy, and retain potential employees in the organization. Effective implementation of talent management is based on the alignment of the top management with the organizational goals to be implemented. Business performance is enhanced through talent management (Altindağ et al., 2018, p.8). The performance of the organization is analyzed in relation to set goals and objectives which resources are aligned for achievement. The employee has the responsibility of harnessing the necessary resources or incentives to optimize job performance and satisfaction through effective management of the workforce (Abolade, 2018, p.8)

Original Article

In the study, employee job performance is measured by reducing employee turnover, employee engagement, and job knowledge. In talent management, employee turnover is a serious concern among organizational leaders who have engaged in reducing the turnover intention in the organization. The continuous loss of employee experience, information, and skills due to turnover has a negative effect on the financial impact of the organization (Najat, 2021, p.1). According to Ramahadhan (2022, p.1), turnover emanates as a result of the inability to implement retention in an effective manner. Therefore, the success of HR decision-making is by understanding the relationship between turnover and retention of workers in an organization (Ramahadhan, 2022, p.2).

Employee engagement harnesses employees with roles in which they express themselves cognitively physically and emotionally based on their role performance. The job roles influence the innovative and cooperative attitude of employees to perform tasks that exceed the set standards of the organization. This is based on the notion that employee engagement is the positive vigor and dedication that workers demonstrate in their work roles. A study by Bolarinwa and Lukman (2022) stress that engaging employees leads to the effective discovery of talent and possible ways of managing them. However, the future of the organization and the achievement of desires and objectives of the organization requires engaging employee in the organization to use available resources to actualize the goals of the organization

Job knowledge influences employee performance through a cognitive ability to achieve organizational goals. It relates to procedure, technical information, and facts needed to perform a given task (Palumbo et al., 2005, p. 15). In the selection of the candidate, a job knowledge test determines the placement, and advancement of the individual in an organization. Job knowledge allows jobs to be analyzed where the individual task, behaviour, and abilities enhance task performance. However, Kuvvas et al. (2016, p.669) view job knowledge as a determinant of employment eligibility in the organization over a given job. In HR practice, job knowledge enhances the process of recruitment, selection, placement, promotion, training, and development for the advancement of organizational goals

Methodology

The study adopted a cross-sectional survey method to ascertain the effect of talent management practices and employee job performance in Niger Mills Company Limited, Calabar, selfstructured questionnaire such as TMPEJP (Talent Management Practice and Employee Job Performance) was used to elicit relevant data for the study. A sample size of 142 staff was surveyed from a population of 221 staff was determined with the use of the Taro Yamane sampling fomular. A four-point Likert scale was used to elicit relevant information.

A total of 142 copies of the questionnaire was administered to senior, supervisory, and junior staff, and 140 were retrieved with a response rate of 98.6 percent which forms the basis of analysis. The adequacy of data was ascertained with the use of a multicollinearity test, and multiple regression was adopted to test the three hypotheses. The use of content and face validity in the study helped to validate the research instrument with the affirmation from research experts, while the Cronbach Alpha Coefficient was used to ascertain the reliability. This is supported by Bonett and Wright (2014, p.3), who opined that the Cronbach Alpha Coefficient is a tool that is widely used for reliability in various areas of discipline. The instrument was apparently fit for data collection with a coefficient of 0, 7 and above (Hair et al., 2014, p.10) as shown in the table below.

Table 1

Coefficient reliability with Cronbach’s Alpha

S/n	Variables	No of items	Cronbach Alpha
1.	Talent retention	5	0.769

Original Article

2.	Job Satisfaction	5	0.895
3.	Training and development	5	0.747
4.	Employee job performance	5	0.829

Source: Source: SPSS Output, 2023

Demographic attributes of respondents

Table 2

Demographic representation of the respondents

<i>Demographic</i>	<i>Total</i>	<i>Percent (%)</i>
Gender		
Male	78	55.7
Female	62	44.3
Total	140	100.0
Age		
20 - 30 years	58	41.4
31 - 40 years	15	17.7
41 – 50 years	41	29.3
51 years and above	26	18.6
Total	140	100.0
Education qualification		
Diploma/NCE	18	12.9
B.Sc/HND	51	36.4
MBA/M.Sc/MA	55	39.3
Ph.D	16	11.4
Total	140	100.0
Marital status		
Single	38	27.2
Married	66	47.1
Divorced	19	13.6
Widow	17	12.1
Total	140	100.0
Working experience		
1-10 years	53	37.9
11 - 20 years	32	22.9
21 years and above	55	39.2

Original Article

Total 140 100.0

Source: Fieldwork, 2023

The table above depicts the distribution of respondents in relation to gender, age, marital status, educational qualification, and working experience. The data obtained for sex distribution revealed that male gender were 78 which represent 55.7 percent; while female were 63 representing 44.2 percent as at the time of the this survey. The age distribution revealed that respondents within the age of 20-30 years were 58 representing 41.4 percent; respondent with the age range of 30-40 were 15 representing 17.7 percent; respondents with the age range of 41-50 age were 41 representing 29.3; while respondent with the age of 51 years and above were 26 representing 18.6 percent. The educational qualification distribution of respondents showed that 18 respondents representing 12.9 percent has Diploma/NCE; 51 respondents representing 36.4 percent had B.Sc./HND; 55 respondents representing 39.3 percent; while 16 respondents representing 11.4 percent has PhD in the organization. This distribution of respondents on the marital status showed that 38 respondents representing 27.2 percent were single; 66 respondents representing 47.1 percent were married; 19 respondents representing 13.6 percent were divorced; while 17 respondents representing 12.1 percent were widowed as at the time of this survey. The distribution of respondents on working experience indicated that 53 respondents representing 37.9 percent has worked between 1-55years; 32 respondents representing 22.9 percent has worked from 11-20 years; 55 respondents representing 39.2 percent has worked over 21 years above.

Result of descriptive statistics of variables

Table 3

Descriptive statistics of human resource management practices and organizational efficiency

Item N Mean Std. Variance

Deviation

Talent retention

Using tested and tried strategies in retaining the best staff helps contribute to the organization's success 140 3.82 1.273 1.571

Intrinsic and extrinsic incentives help to retain talented employees to achieve excellence and competitive advantage in the organization Retaining employees is aimed at enhancing productivity and achieving the set goals of an organization 140 3.66 .847 .851

capacity that makes them unwilling to leave the organization with the acquired talent 140 3.79 .861 .775

Employee willingness to be trained and developed is a core priority of recruiting the workforce into the organization 140 3.98 .963 .785

The increasing pressure on talent makes the organization secure a high-quality talented workforce with potential growth in the labour market 140 3.73 .627 .568

Original Article

Training and development are the140 3.70 .817 .759
 organizational priority for innovation and
 inventions to achieve a competitive
 advantage with worker interest.

Job performance

Increased productivity in the organization is influenced by140 3.82 .858 .747
 performance assessment with feedback on employee performance

Effective management of the workforce140 3.84 .961 .748
 helps to harness the necessary resources
 and incentives to optimize job
 performance

Reducing the turnover intention in the140 3.89 .678 .539
 organization helps to overcome the loss of
 employee experience, information, and
 skills
 which affects the organization

Effective engagement of employee140 3.84 .748 .689
 influence the innovative and cooperative
 attitude to perform tasks that exceed the
 set standards of the organization

Job knowledge influences employee performance 140 3.85 .867 .766
 through a cognitive ability which enhances the

achievement of organizational goals

Source: SPSS Output 2023

The above table discloses descriptive statistics on talent management, and talent retention, job satisfaction, and training and development were used to measure job performance.

Talent retention was measured with a mean of 3.66 and above, and this was linked to all the constructs that measure talent retention which revealed that all the questions were of positive response. Therefore, standard deviation greater than 1 (one) revealed that 68 percent of the variance was obtained from the mean. This confirms adequacy in the spread of the data.

Job satisfaction was measured with a mean of 3.61 and above, and this was linked to all the constructs that measure job satisfaction which revealed that all the questions were of positive response. Therefore, standard deviation greater than 1 (one) revealed that 68 percent of the variance was obtained from the mean. This confirms adequacy in the spread of the data.

Training and development was measured with a mean of 3.70 and above, and this was linked to all the constructs that measure job training and development which revealed that all the questions were of positive response. Therefore, standard deviation greater than 1 (one) revealed that 68 percent of the variance was obtained from the mean. This confirms adequacy in the spread of the data.

Job performance was measured with a mean of 3.82 and above, and this was linked to all the constructs that measure job performance which revealed that all the questions were of positive response. Therefore, standard

Original Article

deviation greater than 1 (one) revealed that 95 percent of the variance was obtained from the mean. This confirms adequacy in the spread of the data

Test of hypotheses

The research hypotheses are as follows:

H₁: Talent retention significantly influence employee job performance in Niger Mills Company Limited Calabar

H₁: Job satisfaction i significantly influence employee job performance in Niger Mills Company Limited Calabar

H₁: Training and development significantly influence employee job performance in Niger Mills Company Limited Calabar

Table 4

Summary of regression analysis

Hypotheses	R	Standardized coefficient B	Collinearity statistics VIF/Tolerance		Test statistic	P value	Significance		
H1	0.865	0.545	2.543	.495	F test= 123.822 T test= 3.741	0.000	Significant		
H2			R ² 0.752	0.756	2.245			.453	F test= 123.822 T test= 11.234
H3				0.692	1.543			.649	F test= 123.822 T test= 8.573

Significant @P≤0.05, Source: Researcher’s data from SPSS

The result of multiple regression analysis on talent management practices and employee job performance in Niger Mills Company Limited Calabar. The “R” column in the above table indicates a correlation between the variables is 0.865 (86 percent) showing a very strong degree of correlation between talent retention and employee job performance. With the multicollinearity test executed, the use of the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) AND tolerance value was aimed at identifying if there are high associations or inter-correlations with the predictor variables. The table depicts the absence of inter-correlations among the predictor variables because the tolerance values and VIF are in consonant with the rule of thumb (Ringle, Wande & Becker, 2015, p.7) which emphasizes that the tolerance should not be lower than 0.1 and VIF should exceed 5.

The R² value (0.752) revealed that up to 75.2 percent of the dependent variable (employee job performance) can be explained by the independent variables (job satisfaction). Hence, this is very significant, and the F test result also indicates that training and development significantly influence employee job performance in Niger Mills Company Limited Calabar (F = 123.822; P < 0.05). Further analysis reveals that there is a significant effect of talent retention, job satisfaction, and training and development on employee job performance in Calabar (EP: t = 3.741, EC: t = 11.234, EF: t = 8.573, EP: β = 0.545, EC: β = 0.756, EF: β = 0.692 and P < 0.05). Therefore, the null hypotheses are rejected while the alternative hypotheses are accepted. This implies that: talent retention, job satisfaction, and training and development significantly influence employee job performance in Niger Mills Company Limited Calabar.

Original Article

Discussion of findings

The result of the regression analysis of the first hypothesis ($\text{Beta} = 0.545, P < 0.05$) indicates that talent retention significantly influences employee job performance in Niger Mills Company Limited Calabar. This is in tandem with the study by El Sayed et al. (2021, p. 646) on the influence of talent management on employee retention which stresses on the effective contribution to organization growth through retention. With a mean of 3.66 and above, the responses of the respondents show that the use of tested and tried strategies in retaining the best staff helps to contribute to the success of the organization. This is a fact because motivating and developing the loyalty of employees, investing in employee careers, and rewarding financial and non-financially. Therefore, in the studied organization, intrinsic and extrinsic incentives help to retain talented employees to achieve excellence and competitive advantage in the organization; retaining employees is aimed at enhancing productivity and achieving the set goals of an organization; quitting job results in loss of customer, loyalty, and employee experience, disruption of activities, and loss of resources which are disastrous to organizational growth; effective identification and stimulation of talent enhance competitive advantage and the present and future success of the organization. Hence, reducing the turnover intention in the organization helps to overcome the loss of employee experience, information, and skills which affects the organization

The result of regression analysis for the second hypothesis ($\text{Beta} = 0.756, P < 0.05$) depicts that job satisfaction significantly influences employee job performance in Niger Mills Company Limited in Calabar, Cross River State. This is in consensus with the study by Gomathy, et al. (2022, p.3) which examined talent management and employee job satisfaction with a view that talented workers can have job satisfaction and be retained through higher pay, work-life balance, job security, and career growth. However, with a mean of 3.61 and above, it is revealed that satisfaction offered to employees makes them share their worthiness and network to achieve the goals and objectives of the organization. This is confirmed to be true because the collective choice of individuals and organizations influences the needed satisfaction. Therefore, in the studied organization, employee engagement influences job satisfaction of employees which enhances business success; payment of higher incentives, adoption of a worklife balance policy, job security, and career growth make them happy with their jobs; increasing levels of responsiveness, high productivity, customer service, and quality are achieved through employee satisfaction; the efficient performance of an organization is driven job satisfaction of employees which makes employees committed to their engagement in the organization. Hence, the increasing pressure on talent makes the organization secure a high-quality talented workforce with potential growth in the labour market

The result of regression analysis for the last hypothesis ($\text{Beta} = 0.692, P < 0.05$) depicts that training and development significantly influence employee job performance in Niger Mills Company Limited in Calabar, Cross River State. This is in line with the study by Tatoglu et al. (2016, p.280) which examined talent management motives and practices in an emerging market with a view that investing in the future of employees through training and development is a strategic source that allows people to undertake their assigned performance for present and future tasks. However, with a mean of 3.70 and above it is revealed that training and development programme available in the organization help to increase employee rate of retention, and career development. This is true because securing a high-quality talented workforce with potential growth in the labour market for competitiveness is through training and development. Therefore, in the studied organization, the continuous learning and growth of employee are capacity that makes them unwilling to leave the organization with the acquired talent; employee willingness to be trained and developed is a core priority of recruiting the workforce into the organization; the increasing pressure on talent make the organization to secure a high-quality talented workforce with potential growth in the labour market; training and development are the organizational priority for innovation and inventions to achieve a competitive advantage with worker interest. Hence, job knowledge influences employee performance through a cognitive ability which enhances the achievement of organizational goals.

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Conclusion

Increased productivity among organizations in a competitive environment requires effective use of resources for talent war and to sustain competitive advantage in the present knowledge drive business environment. This study reviewed the necessity for talent retention, employee job satisfaction, and the effectiveness of training development to harness resources with the right decision to achieve business goals. Hence, the effective management of the workforce in Nihger Mills Company Limited Calabar is by harnessing the necessary resources with incentives to optimize job performance and achieve the set goals of the organization.

Recommendations

Based on the findings the following are recommended:

- 1 The management of the organization should continuously show commitment to talent retention with a policy review based on current realities to help the organization boost productivity with increasing revenue and minimize turnover. To achieve this would require employee experience to enhance competitive advantage.
2. Priority for job satisfaction should be uncompromised to increase morale and productivity through happiness, and a positive workplace culture to enhance effective job performance. To achieve this requires the effective engagement of employee and aligning their talent in the best position to optimize productivity and achievement of organizational goals
3. Training and development should be a continuous practice for competitive advantage with the allocation of resources to improve the company culture and performance level of employees to meet their task. To achieve this requires allowing the employee to achieve job knowledge through their career development and growth/

References

- Abolade, D. A. (2018). Impact of employees' job insecurity and employee turnover on organizational performance in private and public sector organizations. *Studies in Business and Economics*, 13(2), 5–19.
- Akhigbe, O. J. & Chibuogwu, I. B. (2017). Human resource management practices and employee turnover of cable communication firms in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *Funai Journal of Accounting*, 1(1), 47-54
- Al Ariss, A. Cascio, W. F. & Paauwe, J. (2014). Talent management: Current theories and future research directions. *Journal of World Business*, 49(2), 173-179.
- Almohtaseb, A. A., Shaheen, H. A. K. Alomar, K. M. Yousef, M. A. (2020). Impact of talent management on organizational performance: The moderating role of an effective performance management system. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 15(4), 11-27
- Altındağ, E., Çirak, N. Y. & Acar, A. Z. (2018). Effects of talent management components on the employee satisfaction. *Journal of Human Resources Management Research*, 1, 1-20.
- Barney, J. (1991). Firm resources and sustained competitive advantage. *Journal of Management*, 17 (1), 99-120.
- Bolander, P., Werr, A. & Asplund, K. (2017). The practice of talent management: A framework and typology. *Personnel Review*, 46(8), 1523-1561.
- Bolarinwa, K. I. & Lukman, J. A. (2022). *Talent management and employee engagement: A study of Guaranty Trust Bank in Ilorin Metropolis*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/362947378>
- Bonett, B. G. & Wright, T. A. (2014). Cronbach's alpha reliability: Interval estimation, hypothesis testing, and sample size planning. *Journal of Organizational Behaviour*, 1(1), 1-14

Original Article

- Collings, D. G., Mellahi, K. & Cascio, W. F. (2019). Global talent management and performance in multinational enterprises: A multilevel perspective. *Journal of Management*, 45(2), 540–566.
- Covella, G., et al. (2017). Leadership's role in employee retention. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 7(5). 1-15.
- Das, S. P. & Parikh, P. (2007). *Concept and best practices relating to talent management: Human Resource Management*. New Delhi: Excel Books,
- Dixit, S. & Arrawatia, M. A. (2018). The impact of talent management on job satisfaction and employee performance in public sector banks of Rajasthan. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts*, 6(1), 425-436
- Eisen, P., Jasinowski, J. & Kleineli, R. (2005). *Skills gap report - A survey of the American manufacturing workforce*. http://www.doleta.gov/wired/files/us_mfg_talent_management.pdf
- El Sayed, Y. S. N., Wadie, M. R. B. & El Koussy, M. O. (2021). The influence of talent management on employee retention - An empirical study of the Arab Republic of Egypt's Public and Private Commercial Banks. *International Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Change*, 15(10), 640-660
- Farndale, E., Pai, A. Sparrow, P. A & Scullion, H. (2014). Balancing individual and organizational goals in global talent management: A mutual-benefits perspective. *Journal of World Business*, 49(2), 204-214.
- Gomathy, C. K., Tejasw, D. Anvitha, B. & Lokesh, A. (2022). The talent management and employee job satisfaction. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Engineering and Management*, 6(2), 1-5
- Gupta, M. & Haque, M. M. (2015). Talent retention: A major concern for organizations. *Journal of Management*, 7 (4), 19-25.
- Gruman, J. A., & Saks, A. M. (2011). Performance management and employee engagement. *Human Resource Management Review*, 21(2), 123-136
- Hair, J. F., Black Jr., W. C., Babin, B. J. and Anderson, R. E. (2014) *Multivariate Data Analysis*. (7th ed). Harlow, England: Pearson Education Limited.
- Harathova, P. (2009) Enterprise; performance and business processes, perspectives of innovations, economics and business. *Human Resource Journal*, 3(1). 77-83.
- Ibidunni, S., Osibanjo, O. Adeniji, A. Salau, A. P. & Falola, H. (2016). Talent retention and organizational performance: A competitive positioning in Nigerian Banking Sector. *Periodica Polytechnica Social and Management Sciences*, 24(1), 1-13
- Kashive. N., & Khanna. V. T. (2017). Study of early recruitment activities and employer brand knowledge and its effect on organization attractiveness and firm performance. *Global Business Review*, 18(3), 172-190.

Original Article

- Kuvaas, B., Buch, R. Gagné, M. Dysvik, A., & Forest, J. (2016). Do you get what you pay for? Sales incentives and implications for motivation and changes in turnover intention and work effort. *Motivation and Emotion, 40*(5), 667-680.
- Lee, J. Y., Yang, Y. S. & Park. B. I. (2020). Interplay between dual dimensions of knowledge sharing within globalized chaebols: The moderating effects of organization size and global environmental munificence. *International Business Review, 29*(6), 101-116
- Limsangpetch, V., Siripipatthanakul, S. Phayaphrom, B. & Limna, P. (2022). Modelling knowledge management on business performance through mediating role of organizational innovation among IT Staff in Bangkok, Thailand. *International Journal of Behavioral Analytics, 2*(2), 1-17.
- Lockwood, N. R. (2006). *Talent management: Driver for organizational success*. <http://www.shrm.org/research/articles/articles/documents/0606rquartpdf>.
- Meyers, M. C., Van Woerkom, M. & Dries, N. (2013). Talent - innate or acquired? Theoretical considerations and their implications for talent management. *Human Resource Management Review, 23*(4), 305-321.
- Meyers, M. C. & Van Woerkom, M. (2014). The influence of underlying philosophies on talent management: Theory, implications for practice, and research agenda. *Journal of World Business, 49*(2), 192-203.
- Mpofu, M. & Hlatywayo, C. K. (2015). Training and development as a tool for improving basic service delivery; the case of a selected municipality. *Journal of Economics, Finance and Administrative Science, 20*, 133-136
- Naim, M. F. & Lenka, U. J. E (2018). Development and retention of Generation Y employees: A conceptual framework. *Journal of global mobility, 23*(4), 52-59
- Narayanan, A. (2019). Talent management and employee retention: An integrative research framework. *Human Resource Management Review 18*(2), 228-247.
- Najat, M. Y. (2021). *Effect of talent management practices on employee turnover intentions at Nairobi City Water and Sewerage Company*. <http://erepository.uonbi.ac.ke/handle/11295/160997>
- Newbert, S. L. (2007). Value, rareness, competitive advantage, and performance: A conceptual level empirical investigation of the resource-based view of the firm. *Strategic Management Journal, 29*, 745-768.
- Pawirosumarto, S., Sarjana, P. K. & Muchtar, M. (2017). Factors affecting employee performance of PT, Kiyokuni Indonesia. *International Journal of Law and Management, 59*(4), 12-25.
- Palumbo, M. V., Miller, C. E. Shalin, V. L. & Steele-Johnson, D. (2005). The impact of job knowledge in the cognitive ability-performance relationship. *Applied Human Resource Management Research, 10*(1), 13-20
- Ramahadhan, F. (2022). *Employee turnover and retention: The impact of various talent management practices*. <https://www.performancemagazine.org/employee-turnover>

Original Article

- Rani, K. & Kumar, S. (2014). Factors affecting talent management practices: A review. *Indian Journal of Research*, 3(11), 20-23.
- Ringle, C. M., Wande, S. & Becker, J. (2015). *SMARTPLS 3. Bonningstedt: SmartPLS*. <http://www.smartpls.com>
- Sageer, A., Rafat, S., & Agarwal, P. (2012). Identification of variables affecting employee satisfaction and their impact on the organization. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 5(1), 32-39.
- Santhanalaxmi, K. & Chandramohan, S. (2019). Talent management: A tactic to develop organizational performance for business sustainable. *Journal of Scientific Research and Review*, 8(1), 420-426
- Siripipatthanakul, S., Jaipong, P. Limna, P. Sitthipon, T. Kaewpuang, T. Sriboonruang, P. (2022). The impact of talent management on employee satisfaction and business performance in the digital economy: A qualitative study in Bangkok, Thailand. *Advance Knowledge for Executive* 1(1), 1-17
- Tanwar, I. K. & Prasad, A. (2016). The effect of employer brand dimensions on job satisfaction: Gender as a moderator. *Management Decision*, 54(4), 12-23
- Tarique, I. & Schuler, R. (2017). A multi-level framework for understanding global talent management systems for high-talent expatriates within and across subsidiaries of MNEs. *Journal of Global Mobility*, 6(1), 79-101.
- Tatoglu, E. A., Glaister, A. J. & Demirbag, M. C. (2016). Talent management motives and practices in an emerging market: A comparison between MNEs and local firms. *Journal of World Business*, 51(2), 278-293.
- Tyskbo, D. (2019). Talent management in a Swedish public hospital. *Personnel review*, (48)6, 1611-1633.